

ANALYSIS OF RETURNS TO SOCIAL CAPITAL AMONG TIMBER MARKETERS IN ONDO STATE.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the returns to social capital among timber marketers in Ondo State. Purposive sampling was used in the data collection as four sawmills was identified and one hundred and twenty respondents were randomly selected from the sawmills. Questionnaire was used to obtain information from the marketers. Results show that over 75% of the members attend meetings regularly with an index of between 20 and 50 percent of the highest time allocated to meeting attendance. The decision-making index of the respondents' shows that members with the highest decision making index have high social capital than those with low or intermediate index and are most committed to the course of the association. Result shows that marketers with high income from the business tends to be more involved in local association activities as a result of social capital accumulated. Social capital dimension shows that index of participation and cash contribution was significant at 10 percent showing that as respondents participate in local association activities more social capital was accumulated.

KEY WORDS: Social capital, gross margin, marketing, local association

INTRODUCTION

Social capital has become a topic of interest in a large number of policy areas. Definitions vary but it is often understood to be a social resource which is created through formal and informal relationships between people within a community. It describes the social environment that people live in, and is the collective resources to which individuals, families, neighbourhoods and communities have access. The World Bank (1999) defines social capital as the institutions, relationship and norms that shape the quality and quantity of a society interaction. Increasing evidence show that social cohesion is critical for societies to prosper economically and for development to be sustainable.

Social capital has been found to have great impact on the income and welfare of the poor, by improving the outcome of activities that affects them. Rural people coming together to achieve a common goal through social capital, will improve the efficiency of rural development programs by increasing agricultural productivity, facilitation, the management of common resources making rural trading more profitable and improve access of people or household to water, sanitation, credit and education in rural and urban areas (Grootaert and Bastelaer, 2001). This is why social capital refers to connections among "individuals" and the "social networks" of reciprocity that arises from them.

Social capital is one among several factors of production, along with human capital, financial capital, physical and natural resources (Crudeli, 2005; Grootaert and Narayan, 1999; Serageldin 1996). Thus, there is a growing recognition (Grootaert, 2005, Okunmadewa *et al*, 2004) that difference in economic outcomes, whether at the level of the individual or household or at the level of the state, cannot be explained fully by difference in the "traditional" inputs such as labour, land and physical capital. The role of social capital plays in affecting the well being of household and the level of development of communities and nations are been documented (Serageldin 1996 and Grootaert, 1999), these scholars argued that social capital is an input in a household's or a nation's productions and has major implications for development policy and project design. This suggests that acquisition of human capital and establishment of physical infrastructure needs to be complemented by institutional development in order to reap the full benefits of the investments (Grootaert, 1999, Svendsen, 2000; Knack 1999). Social capital describes activities familiar in everyday life in rural and pre-industrial societies around the world, cooperation between individuals within their household and outside it to meet their everyday needs (Halpern, 2001). Yet social capital has not been easily accounted for in the money terms (Woolcock, 2001), its significance has tended to be overlooked

(Lorenz, 1988). However, it ought to be of major importance in developing countries like Nigeria where so much economic activity is not yet fully monetized and extended family ties are primary (Okunmadewa *et al*, 2004). Certainly, the case for massive investment in social capital has been made, investing in social capital, although, there are number of time-tested approaches in investing in social capital that are available such as building schools, training teachers, developing appropriate curricula and so forth. Equivalent which have proven fruitful but documentation in investing in social capital have not yet emerged (Grootaert and Bestelaer, 2001).

Consequently, this study is designed to assess returns to social capital among timber marketers in Ondo State, specifically; the study developed a social capital index and the index was used to categories social capital formation available to marketers in the study area, evaluate the effect of social capital index on gross margin, assess the degree of linkage between social capital and income of timber marketers.

METHODOLOGY

Area of Study

This study was conducted in Ondo State of Nigeria (2009). Ondo State is situated in the south western geo-political region of Nigeria, which comprises of 18 Local Government Areas. The state has a land area of 14,973 square kilometer and projected population of 5,691,843 (NPC, 1991). It is bounded in the North by Ekiti and Kogi State, in the East by Edo and Delta States, in the West by Osun and Ogun State and in the south by the Atlantic Ocean. Ondo State falls within the tropical forest with total rainfall of about 1,250mm-1,500mm annually and it has a bio-modal distribution between April-August and August-November. The maximum temperature ranges between 12°C-23°C, while humidity is relatively high.

Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Ondo State. Majority of the people in the area are producers who produce and market some agricultural produce like maize, rice, yam, plantain, tomato *e. t. c.* including livestock production. The people are predominantly farmers. The farming population is scattered all over the villages in the Local Government Areas.

Sources of Data

The data for this study were obtained mainly from primary sources. Information was collected on the socio-economic/demographic characteristics of food marketers, costs and returns of each timber marketer, social capital indices such as level of trust, Heterogeneity index, Density of membership, meeting attendance and active participation index.

Sampling Procedure

The study covers Akure South Local Government Area of Ondo State. Since timber marketing is a lucrative business in Ondo State, four sawmills were chosen from the Local Government, they are at Ogbese, Oba-ile, Ilaramakin and Awule. From each of the sawmill, thirty marketers was randomly selected to make a sample size of 120 respondents.

Analytical Techniques

The analytical framework for this study includes descriptive, gross margin and regression analyses. The descriptive analysis encompasses frequency distribution, mean, median and mode as well as coefficient of variation. In addition, different social capital dimension indices are constructed. The regression analysis attempts to model the Social Capital Index through identifying and listing of all social capital dimensions attaching scores and weight respectively. Social capital index (SCI), Human Capital (HC) and Socio-economic variables (SEV) of the marketers were measured against their Gross margin/Total sales.

The Gross margin analysis is used to determine the profitability of the business. It is the difference between the Total Revenue and the Total variable cost.

$$\text{Gross margin} = \text{Total Revenue} - \text{Total variable Cost}$$

The regression analysis is further elaborated upon in the subsequent paragraphs.

The implicit form of the model is given by

$$Q = f(\text{SCI}, \text{HC}, \text{SEV})$$

Where Q= Gross Margin/Total sale as dependent variable

SCI= Social capital index

HU= Human Capital

SEV= Socio-economic variables

Variables Definition

(A) The social capital variables that were used in the regression analysis include:

The indices used are density of membership, heterogeneity index, meeting attendance index, cash contribution, labour contribution and decision making index. The measurement of these six social capital indices is as explained below. This follows the approach used by Grootaert, *et al* (2002). The measurement of each is as described below.

1. Density of membership: this is captured by the summation of the total number of associations to which each household belongs. In other words, the membership of associations by individuals in the household is summed up.

2. Heterogeneity index: this is an aggregation of the responses of each household to the questions on the diversity of members of the most important institutions to the households.

3. Meeting attendance index: this is obtained by summing up the attendance of household members at meetings and relating it to the number of scheduled meetings by the associations they belong to.

4. Cash contribution: This was obtained by the summation of the total cash contributed to the various associations which the household belong.

5. Labour contribution: this is the number of days that household members belonging to institutions claimed to have worked for their institutions.

6. Decision making index: this was calculated by summation of the subjective responses of households on their rating in the participation in the decision making of the three most important institutions to them.

Aggregate social capital index: this is obtained by the multiplication of density of membership, heterogeneity index and decision making index (Grootaert, 1999). The resultant index is renormalized to maximum value of 100.

(B) The human capital variable was measured by the average years of formal education of the head of the household.

(C) The household characteristics used are:

(i) Marital status of household head (1 if married, 0 if otherwise)

(ii) Household size (actual number of people in the household)

(iii) Gender of household head (D=1 if male, 0 if otherwise)

(iv) Age of household head in years

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selected Household Characteristics and Dimensions of Social Capital.

Selected Household Characteristics of Respondents: Table 1 presents the selected socio-economic characteristics of the sampled respondents. Most of the marketers selected are male (79.2%) while 20.8% of the marketers are female; the competing demand for production and reproduction may be responsible for low involvement (Adekoya, 2007). Age-wise, most of the respondents are in their economic active age. Most of the marketers are in the middle age falling between 36-55years (60%). This implies that risk element could be potent in the enterprise, in that is assumed that the older the marketers the more risk averse he becomes. Table 1 also shows that the marketers have household

size of between 5-10 members this implies that the respondents have a relatively large family. This may be as a result of the need to have more helping hands with the business.

The level of educational attainment shows that majority of the respondents had access to formal education, 88.4% had one form of formal education or the other, the recorded level of education might influence marketer's level of exposure and be more involved in social activities.

Table 1 also shows that majority of the marketers had between 1-10 years of experience in the business (59.9%), while 25.8% have been into timber marketing for over 10years. The result implies that more experience people are involved in the business and this enables them to relate more with each other and build a strong trust among themselves.

Table 1: Selected Household Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	95	79.2
Female	25	20.8
Age:		
26-36yrs	9	7.5
36-45yrs	45	37.5
46-55yrs	27	22.5
Above 55yrs	39	32.5
Household size		
Less than 5	25	20.8
5-10	83	70.7
Above 10	10	8.5
Level of Education		
No formal education	14	11.6
Primary	35	29.1
Secondary	45	37.4
Tertiary	20	16.6
Others specify	6	5.0
Years of Experience		
1-10yrs	72	59.9
11-20yrs	31	25.8
21-30yrs	17	14.2
Total	120	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2009

Social Capital index

Table 2 shows the social capital index, the result shows that majority of the marketers belong to at least one association in the study area. While 16.6% belong to 2-3 association in the area. This shows that the marketers belong to least one local association where they interact. On the cash contribution of the marketers, the results shows that about 79.8% contribute less than 4 percents of total cash contribution, while 20% contribute more than 4 percent of the highest cash contribution within the study area. The labour contribution index shows that 70% of the marketers gave less than 20 percent of the highest time allocated to any local association in the study area, while 30% gave more than 20 percent of the highest time allocated to any association within the study area. The Heterogeneity index involve using socio-economic factors such as religion, age, level of education, gender to construct heterogeneity index, this depicts the internal homogeneity of the group. The result shows that about 21.6% of the marketers have an heterogeneity index of less than 20 in their local associations and about 28.2% have an heterogeneity index of between 20 and 50 while 50.% of the marketers were on heterogeneity index that is greater than 50. A high degree of heterogeneity in an association usually has negative implication, because it makes it more difficult for members to trust each other, since it implies lesser degree of homogeneity. In term of meeting

attendance, it seem that meetings are most frequent in the study area occurring on the average, every ten days, the table shows that the higher the meeting attendance index by members, the more the participation in the association's activities. The result shows that over 75% of the members attend meetings more regularly with an index of between 20 and 50 percent of the highest time allocated to meeting attendance. The decision-making index of the respondents' shows that members with the highest decision making index have high social capital than those with low or intermediate index. This may be so because those with high decision making index are likely to be most committed to the course of the association and those with very low value of decision making index, they seem not to be committed to the activities of the associations and hence lower social capital. The result shows that 82.5% of the marketers have above 20 percent decision making index.

Table 2: Social Capital Indices

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Density of Association		
Less than 2	92	76.5
2-3	20	16.6
Above 3	8	6.6
Cash Contribution		
Less than 4	96	79.8
4-10	15	12.5
11-20	6	5.0
Above 20	3	2.5
Labour Contribution		
Less than 20	74	70.0
20-50	27	12.5
Above 50	9	7.8
Heterogeneity Index		
Less than 20	26	21.6
20-50	34	28.2
Above 50	60	50.0
Meeting Attendance		
Less than 20	27	22.7
20-50	90	75.0
Above 50	3	2.5
Decision Making		
Less than 20	9	7.8
20-50	84	70.0
Above 50	27	12.5
Total	120	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

Gross Margin Analysis

Gross margin is used to determine the profitability of the business. It is the difference between the Total Revenue and the Total variable cost.

$$\text{Gross margin} = \text{Total Revenue} - \text{Total variable Cost}$$

The total revenue is the amount of money collected by the timber merchants on the sale of timber. The total variable cost is the cost incurred in the running of the business which include labour, wages, offices and administrative expensive, fueling and vehicle maintenance, electricity dues e.t.c.

Result of Cost and Returns Analysis

Total variable Cost	₦65026800
Total Revenue	₦287292400
Gross Margin	₦222265600
Gross Margin per marketer =	$\frac{\text{Total Gross margin}}{\text{Number of marketer}}$
=	$\frac{222265600}{120}$
=	₦1852213.33

From the result, the total variable cost was ₦65026800 while the total revenue was ₦287292400, when the gross margin per marketer was ₦1852213.33. The size and positive value obtained from the gross margin confirmed that timber marketing was able to cover the operating expense therefore profitable in the study area.

Regression Analysis

Table 3 and 4 show the effect of socio-economic variables, human capital variable and social capital index variables on respondent's gross margin. The education variables in Table 3 was disintegrated into primary, secondary and tertiary variables, while the aggregate social capital index was disintegrated into its components indices, which are Heterogeneity index, decision making index, cash contribution index, labour contribution index, meeting attendance, index of participation in Table 4.

(a) Socio-Economic variables

From Table 3, two of the five variables in the index were significant and these are years of experience (at 5percent) and years of education (at 5percent). The interpretation of the result shows that years of experience in the business enhance participation in social association because of the benefit derived from the association which in turns increase the profit realized from the business. Also the result suggests that being educated and accumulating social capital would improve the performance on the business. This is so since the higher the level of education of the marketers the more their human capital and thus increased income.

The insignificant variables are sex, age, and family size at 5percent this is because sex does not affect participation in local association in the study area. Age of the respondents have little effect on the social capital formation.

(b) Human Capital variable

The human capital variable considered is the years of education and result from table 3 confirm that it is an important variable, thus impact accumulating social capital in the area. This shows that the more educated the respondents are the more social capital they can accumulate.

(c) Social Capital Index variables

In Table 3, the social capital index does not have a significant effect on the marketers gross margin, however variables such as index of participation, cash contribution, were significant at 10 percent level of significance. The implication of these findings is that the proportion of participation and cash contribution of the respondents increase in association, so will more social capital be accumulated. Also labour contribution and Heterogeneity index is significant at 5percent.

Table 3 Regression Analysis Result I

Variables	Coefficient Parameter	Standard Error	t-ratio	IP/(T/>t)
Constant	-254.364	222.067	-1.145	.2540
Sex	40.061	33.132	1.239	.1785
Age	6.694	8.234	.754	.4607
Family size	-5.546	7.923	-.557	.450
Years of Experience	5.498	2.023	1.304	.033**
Years of Education	56.410	27.678	1.864	.543**
Social Capital index	0.0057	2.18	-1.479	.1234
Membership in Association	0.0825	0.432	0.581	0.543
Index of Participation	1.869	5.858	0.319	0.750*
Heterogeneity index	0.427	0.736	0.580	0.563
Meeting Attendance	-1.214	0.710	-1.609	0.034
Cash Contribution	0.231	1.347	0.145	0.0765*
Labour Contribution	0.979	1.157	0.787	0.392

Source: Field Survey Data 2009,* Significant at 5%, ** Significant 10%

Table 4 Regression Analysis Result II

Variables	Coefficient Parameter	Standard Error	t-ratio	IP/(T/>t)
Constant	-203.032	211.324	-.823	0.321
Sex	87.761	34.453	1.002	0.245
Age	6.354	9.342	0.761	0.423
Tertiary Education	89.91	45.34	2.120	0.035
Primary Education	26.76	42.341	0.542	0.4304
Secondary Education	41.353	45.042	0.931	0.346
Social Capital index	0.0014	0.054	2.18	0.123
Membership in Association	0.0741	0.321	0.831	0.435
Index of Participation	1.869	5.858	0.419	0.650
Heterogeneity index	0.474	0.643	0.580	0.563
Meeting Attendance	-1.134	0.510	-1.739	0.052
Cash Contribution	0.361	1.256	0.134	0.0589
Labour Contribution	0.798	1.231	0.864	0.278

Source: Field Survey Data 2009.

CONCLUSION

Social capital has been found to have great impact on the income and welfare of the poor, by improving the outcome of activities that affects them. Rural people coming together to achieve a common goal through social capital accumulation. As empirical findings from this study show that marketers with high income from the business tends to be more involved in local association as a result of the social capital accumulated. Social capital dimension shows that index of participation and cash contribution was significant at 10 percent showing that as respondents participate in local association more social capital was accumulated. Also labour contribution and Heterogeneity index was significant at 5percent showing that marketers are more directly involved in the activities of the local association which will influence social capital accumulation.

The income realized shows that timber marketing is a profitable venture in the area, this influence participation in local association as shown in the cash contribution of the marketers, income generated from one's business activities enable the people to participate in local association and this in turn influences social capital accumulation.

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